

Instrument to Instrument (ITI) Translation Tool

Abstract:

Satellite-based observations are crucial for many research areas, but instrument differences (spatial and temporal resolution, spectral channels, noise levels etc.) make combining different data sources into homogeneous datasets challenging. In this work, we present a machine learning (ML) tool for Instrument-to-Instrument (ITI) translation (Jarolim et al. 2023), with the goal of inter-calibrating and homogenizing image data collected by different instruments for Earth observation and heliophysics applications. Our ITI framework is built on generative models that enable intercalibration, image enhancement, degradation correction, and super-resolution across multiple spectral bands.

ITI is provided open-source to the community and can be easily applied to novel datasets and various research applications. Our goals are to learn and share best practices through early and ongoing involvement from the scientific community to ensure we are building the right tool for downstream applications, whilst maintaining the ability to adapt as we learn more about how to use emerging tools, applications, and limitations that become apparent in the process.

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Instrument to Instrument (ITI) Translation

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1. Project Overview

The 'ITI' (Instrument to Instrument Translation) tool supports instrument-to-instrument translation of images across different domains. This is a recurring problem whereby one has a large number of heterogeneous datasets exhibiting different signal characteristics from different domains. The development of this tool will allow users to **translate** multi-dimensional images from one sensor domain to a second sensor domain. This tool is attractive because the domains can exhibit widely different spatiotemporal and signal characteristics. We believe this tool is useful for many domains outside of just heliophysics (as shown in Jarolim et al. 2024, under revision) as this is a recurring problem within the heliophysics and geosciences community.

Image-to-Image translation is a common downstream use case for example, as well as super-resolution and instrument calibration. Additionally, this ITI tool will allow users to **combine** different data from different instruments. This can potentially facilitate the creation of homogenized datasets with new and historical satellite data sets. This can unlock the underused potential of archival data which will allow users to combine insights from different satellite and instrument observations. This ITI tool can be used as a general AI tool to create joint data products in service of major open science questions.

This project will mature the ITI tool from TRL 5 (lab-tested system) to TRL 6 (field-tested prototype) allowing ITI to be used in a myriad of applications that currently do not have a rapid and effective way to combine data from disparate instruments. ITI is a critical enabling component of collaborative sensor networks, where multiple instruments are used in concert - *a so-called "sensor web"*.

ITI will be matured from TRL 5 to TRL 6 by improving the interface, making the tool more accessible to the community, specifically non-specialist data scientists, building integrated validation and monitoring workflows, and extending its utility into multiple domains, with an initial focus on Heliophysics and Earth Observation (EO).

Fig. 1: The primary model architecture of ITI, which consists of a module which transforms a dataset from sensor A to generate a dataset B which shares the same characteristics of data generated from sensor A.

Fig. 2: The heliophysics use case for the ITI tool. In this case, the ITI tools are used to do image-to-image translation of a SOHO image to a SDO image.

Fig. 3: The remote sensing use case for the ITI tool. In this case, the ITI tools are used to do image-to-image translation between different geostationary satellites.

Overview of how ITI works currently: The primary model architecture consists of two neural networks. The first generates synthetic low-quality images from a given high-quality image (generator BA). The second network is trained to invert the image degradation to reconstruct the original high-quality observation (generator AB). The mapping in the target domain is enforced with the use of a discriminator network. An additional noise factor is included for generator BA to model a variety of degrading effects, independent of the image content. With the synthesis of more realistic and diverse low-quality observations, the generator AB is capable of providing a similar reconstruction performance for real low-quality observations.

Fig. 4: The primary model architecture of ITI, which consists of two neural networks

The ITI pipeline requires no alignment of the data sets; enabling translation between instruments that have no joined observing periods, or have differences in their spatial alignment.

2. Science Use Cases

We have expanded ITI into relevant science use cases in both Heliophysics and Earth Observation. Throughout the expansion process, we modularized the code and documented the process so that additional use cases can be added in the future.

Heliophysics Use Cases:

ITI has previously been applied to five different Heliophysics use cases and implements a framework for loading different solar observatory data, including SDO/AIA+HMI, Hinode/SOT, SoHo/EIT+MDI, STEREO/EUVI, and KSO (H-alpha). The method has demonstrated the ability to homogenize data sets, provide stable enhancement of solar images and restoration of long-term image time series. The demonstrated heliophysics examples include translations between instruments with different field-of-view, resolution and calibration.

In this project, we have expanded ITI to three additional use cases:

Solar Orbiter Full Sun Imager (EUI/FSI) to Solar Dynamics Observatory AIA (SDO/AIA)

The first use case we will apply ITI to is the translation between the Full Sun Imager (FSI) on the EUI instrument aboard the Solar Orbiter mission and the AIA instrument on SDO.

- FSI provides an angular resolution of 10 arcsec at a cadence of 15 min (synoptic mode) and uses two filter wavelength channels (174 and 304 AA).

- SDO's AIA instrument provides solar full-disc images with a spatial resolution of 1.5 arcsec, recorded by 4096x4096 pixel CCDs, operating at a cadence of 12 seconds and provides EUV filtergrams in seven band passes.

Combining both missions into a unified data set will facilitate co-temporal usage, which enables the consistent study of solar events from multiple viewpoints. Given the limited number of spatially and temporally aligned observations, our ITI approach allows us to calibrate the data for joint use.

Solar Orbiter High Resolution Imager (EUI/HRI) to Solar Dynamics Observatory AIA (SDO/AIA)

The second case study focuses on the translation between SDO/AIA to Solar Orbiter/EUI/HRI.

- The HRI instrument provides observations with a two pixel resolution of 1 arcsec in the two wavelength channels 174 AA and 304 AA. Due to the varying orbit of Solar Orbiter it can provide observation with $(100 \text{ km})^2$ in the perihelion.
- In contrast, SDO/AIA captures full Sun observation with a spatial resolution of 1.5 arcsec per pixel.

This offers the possibility to obtain super-resolved full Sun observation by training SDO/AIA on data from the Solar Orbiter/EUI/HRI instrument.

PROBA2 Sun Watcher using Active Pixel System detector and Image Processing (SWAP) to Solar Dynamics Observatory AIA (SDO/AIA)

In order to enhance observations of the SWAP instrument on board of PROBA2 we use SDO/AIA observations as reference.

- SWAP provides full Sun observations with a resolution of 3.16 arcsec in the 174 AA channel.

Enhancing SWAP observations to SDO/AIA quality provides detailed observations at full resolution, but also at smaller scales.

Heliophysics Use Case Downstream users:

Image enhancement. With technological improvements, the quality of space-based telescopes has improved in recent years. However, for solar variability studies we need joint and dataproducts. With unpaired image-to-image translation, ITI can restore and enhance solar observations for combined usage.

Instrument intercalibration. Multi-viewpoint observations are necessary for detailed studies of solar phenomena. The intercalibration of multiple instruments enables combined studies from different viewpoints, e.g. Solar Orbiter and SDO.

Super-resolution. In order to study small scale features, high spatial resolution observations are needed. By translating SDO/AIA observation to HRI observations in the perihelion, we can provide full Sun super-resolved observations in the SDO perspective.

Earth Observation Use Cases:

To fully demonstrate the potential of our framework, we are investigating two Earth observation use cases: (1) intercalibration of geostationary satellites, and (2) translation between geostationary and polar-orbiting satellites. In the first case, we translate the

Spinning Enhanced Visible and Infrared Imager (SEVIRI) instrument onboard the Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) satellites to the characteristics of the Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) onboard NOAA's Geostationary Operational Environmental (GOES) satellite.

MSG/SEVIRI performs measurements over Europe and Africa in 11 spectral channels and with a sub-satellite resolution of 3 km, while GOES/ABI is centered over the Americas and measures 16 spectral channels with a sub-satellite resolution of 2 km. Due to the high temporal cadence of geostationary satellites, where full-disk images are captured every 10-15 mins, they are particularly suited as weather satellites.

For our second use case, we translate between the characteristics of GOES/ABI and NASA's Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MODIS), which has collected a wealth of data onboard the polar-orbiting AQUA and TERRA satellites. Geostationary satellites like GOES measure the Earth and the atmosphere with high temporal resolution, but compared to e.g. MODIS, have a lower spatial resolution and fewer spectral channels. For many downstream applications, for instance studying clouds in the atmosphere, high temporal resolutions are crucial. Compared to GOES/ABI, MODIS performs measurements in swaths with 1 km spatial resolution and across 36 spectral channels. Due to the near-polar orbit, MODIS performs global measurements but only revisits specific points on Earth once a day. In comparison, GOES/ABI has a limited field-of-view but performs measurements every 15 mins. Combining the characteristics of both instruments enables the creation of datasets with high spatial, spectral, and temporal resolution. Similarly, the inter-calibration of geostationary satellites enables the creation of global datasets with 15 mins cadence that can be used, for instance, to study cloud evolution and dynamics across the world.

EO Use Case Downstream users:

Feature Extraction/Foundation Models. The rs-tools package provides analysis-ready (clean, harmonized scenes) data and ml-ready data (clean patches) which can easily be applied for a wide range of use cases involving level 1 data. Users can try to train their own general feature extractors (i.e., foundation models) or, once these are already trained, they can take the pretrained weights to be applied for other downstream tasks like classification, segmentation or estimation.

Intercalibration. Intercalibration of geostationary satellites would enable creating (near-)global datasets of the atmosphere that could be used to study cloud evolution at high temporal resolution across the Earth. This could be useful for a variety of research areas, including the Cloud/Aerosol community, and would provide more robust observational constraints for global (high-resolution) climate models.

Cloud Retrieval. Potential downstream users from the cloud/aerosol community could use ITI to translate GOES to the characteristics of MODIS for a number of applications. For instance, the cloud and aerosol retrieval algorithms of MODIS are used to study aerosol-cloud interactions. However, clouds evolve on timescales faster than the 1-2 day revisit time of the instrument, making it difficult to study the temporal evolution of clouds. While GOES provides the desired temporal resolution, GOES images are at significantly lower spatial resolution than MODIS, and comparisons to ground-based aerosol

measurements showed that GOES aerosol retrievals are less accurate than MODIS retrievals. Demonstrating a successful translation from GOES to MODIS images, or directly to the MODIS cloud and aerosol retrievals would be greatly beneficial in this context.

3. Software

The software for the ITI tool is configured to work with use cases in Heliophysics and Earth Observation; following standard software engineering practices with the following components: a) data ingestion, preprocessing, and analysis-ready data, b) model training, c) model deployment and inference, d) visualization, e) validation and analysis, and f) documentation and tutorials.

The primary features of the ITI are:

- Universal tool for domain translation of satellite data that allows:
 - Easy access to analysis ready, harmonized data from various NASA satellites and other sources.
- Data Acquisition for Heliophysics and Earth Observation Data
- Instrument intercalibration
- Image super-resolution
- Mitigation of degrading effects (image enhancement)

We wrote modular and reusable software to harmonize Earth Observation data ([rs_tools](#)) and Heliophysics data ([helio_tools](#)) and create cleaned data that easily fits in the existing ITI framework. All code needed to clean and prepare solar observations for translation, in addition to the actual ITI translation tool itself, can be found in the [InstrumentToInstrument](#) repository on GitHub.

3.a Data Ingestion, Preprocessing and Analysis-Ready Data

Heliophysics:

The Heliophysics pipeline provides download routines, preprocessing editors, ML-ready datasets, training and evaluation modules for all applied case studies.

Downloading

These are python scripts where a user can download data from an external database, including custom data downloaders such as the ITI data-download script for the [SDO](#) module for all use cases. We also have some [publicly available test data](#) which will allow users to play around with a subset of the datasets available without downloading the entire database.

Preprocessing

A large portion of these preprocessing functions operate on custom .fits structures and/or numpy arrays. For the .fits structures, we make use of sunpy functions which can manipulate the .fits-file using domain-specific transformations, e.g. normalization, header manipulation, and/or coordinate transformations. For the numpy arrays, these are more ML-esque transformations like normalization, padding and/or nan-removal. A significant portion of this

has already been done within the ITI repo (see the [editor.py](#) module). PyTorch DataLoaders and PyTorch-Lightning DataModules, e.g., see [SDO](#) example within the ITI [dataset.py](#) module.

Analysis Ready Data

The ML-ready datasets consist of stacked pre-processing editors, which are depending on the instrument one is using. The dataloaders are built on PyTorch Lightning, simplifying the training process.

Earth Observation:

The EO modular preprocessing pipeline contains tools to download, geoprocess, and patch Earth Observation satellite data. All components are implemented and tested for the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites ([GOES](#)), the Meteosat Second Generation ([MSG](#)) satellites, and the [TERRA](#) and [AQUA](#) satellites.

Downloading:

Our downloaders build on existing packages like [goes-2-go](#), [EarthAccess](#) and [eumdac](#). For each downloader, we added functionality to select specific dates and times, and allow filtering for measurements conducted during certain times of the day. This is particularly helpful for filtering day- and nighttime measurements. In addition to downloading Level-1 data, all downloaders have been expanded and tested for downloading cloud masks.

Geoprocessing:

Our geoprocessing pipeline reads in raw data files, and performs the following operations:

- Match data & cloudmask timestamps
- Load radiances
- Stack data channels
- Attach latitude / longitude information in native coordinate reference system
- Attach cloudmask
- Attach band wavelengths
- Attach measurement time
- Optional: Resample to different resolution
- Optional: Crop region

Our geoprocessing pipeline outputs standardized netcdf datafiles for all satellites that contain coordinate information, stacked band data, cloudmasks, and relevant metadata.

Patching:

Our patching operator takes in standardized netcdf files and creates unpaired, machine learning ready data patches that can be saved in either netcdf or numpy format. The patching is done through striding.

Integration into the ITI tool

We developed a GeoDataset and editors that plug into the existing ITI Dataloader. Our GeoDataset loads our geoprocessed and standardized netcdf files, and returns a dictionary of `coords`, `data`, `cloudmask`, and `wavelengths`. All our editors process these dictionaries and perform operations on relevant keys. In detail, we developed the following editors

- `BandOrderEditor`: Allows reordering bands based on specified target order.
- `BandSelectionEditor`: Allows selecting specific bands.

- NanMaskEditor: Attaches nan mask for data
- NanDictEditor: Fills in nan values
- CoordNormEditor: Normalizes latitude / longitude coordinates to [-1, 1]
- RadUnitEditor: Converts radiance units from $\text{mW}/\text{m}^2/\text{sr}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ to $\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{sr}/\text{um}$
- StackDictEditor: Stacks all data together and converts dictionary to numpy array

3.b Model Training

We provide a set of detailed training scripts which 1) initialize the LightningAI DataModule based on the specification of the dataset and appropriate preprocessing routines, 2) build a LightningAI Learner module based on the specified model architecture, loss, and optimizer, 3) train a model until convergence, 4) save the model weights for later use in wandb. This provides the user with a detailed specification of the end-to-end process from data to trained model. This portion is application agnostic but we provide the model configurations and specifications used in a successful demonstration for the user case. It features a detailed config file (.yaml) for the individual (hyper-)parameters of the data, preprocessing, model specification, optimizer, loss function, training, callbacks, hardware specifications and postprocessing routines. Many ML researchers and experts alike will find this useful because it will provide a reproducible specification to establish some baselines. We use weights and biases (wandb) as a logging platform to showcase our training procedure and saved weights that are available to other users.

Heliophysics:

For all use cases we provide training scripts and the corresponding *config* files to start the training process. For logging loss curves, visualizing example images during training and tracking the training process, the wandb platform is used.

Earth Observation:

We provide a training specification for the outlined EO-specific use cases. For users interested in performing their own training, there will be Hydra integration to allow easily configurable training scripts. We also showcase logged callbacks including loss curves, metrics and images of some predictions for the training phase. The saved model weights are stored on wandb and the associated config for reproducibility.

3.c Model Deployment and Inference

We will provide a set of detailed inference scripts which will allow users to download previously trained models from specified use cases and apply them on an evaluation (or completely different) dataset. This will 1) load a LightningAI data module for evaluation, 2) load a pre-trained LightningAI learner based on a config + weights provided by wandb, 3) perform inference on the evaluation dataset, and 4) save the results to an appropriate output file (e.g. FITS or TIFF). This will provide the user with a detailed specification of the end-to-end process from data to predictions with a pretrained model. This process will also provide API access to inference endpoints for deployed trained models.

Heliophysics: We have trained models for image enhancement (PROBA2/SWAP-to-SDO/AIA), instrument intercalibration (Solo/EUI/FSI-to-SDO/AIA), and

the super-resolution case study (SDO/AIA-to-SolO/EUI/HRI). These models and associated training steps will be made available in the [Instrument-to-Instrument repository](#).

Earth Observation: With the development of our GeoDataset and editors, we have created a functioning ITI pipeline for Earth Observation data. As our next steps, we are training models for various experimental configurations to test how well ITI works for Earth Observation data. While the current training pipelines follow the same formatting originally developed for ITI, we will also create modular hydra training pipelines for future expansions of the ITI framework.

3.d Visualization.

A minimal amount of visualization tools will be provided for each use case. This can be in the form of prediction maps from the model versus the original dataset. It will also showcase the results from comparable baselines to give the users an idea of how their method performs. The format will be through jupyter notebooks as it will allow some interactivity for users. In addition, we can provide a file of (light) saved images which we can display in a simple github repo or google drive for users to download.

Heliophysics: We prepared helper functions to simplify the translation and visualization process for the users. This includes:

1. the loading of the data with the preprocessing steps necessary for the translation,
2. the translation itself, and
3. a simple visualization function for the comparison between the original, ground truth and the ITI translated observation.

In addition, for the instrument intercalibration case studies, we added image intensity calculation functions with corresponding visualization.

To provide analysis-ready data, we added a save function that saves the Sunpy maps as *.fits* files. The translation process already includes an update and translation of the metadata. Saving to the *.fits* format therefore allows all the necessary information to be stored in a single file, including image and metadata.

Earth Observation: We are still working on developing pairing approaches to spatially and temporally match data collected by different satellites. We are also still in the process of developing domain agnostic metrics that will allow us to better evaluate our model output. This involves calculating metrics across different spatial scales, separate regions (e.g., northern hemisphere, southern hemisphere) and different data pixel-types (e.g. over land or ocean, with or without clouds).

3.e Validation and Analysis.

End-user scientists must be able to trust the ITI toolkit to conserve critical properties of the data in a self-consistent way. For example, the noise-properties of the translated data should remain capable of representing the confidence of the predicted image. Alternatively, a separate confidence map should be generated to inform any downstream analysis, especially if the downstream task makes use of generative AI analysis. The danger here is

that stacked AI workflows can generate completely plausible artifacts that are indistinguishable from real signals.

Tools and synthetic data should be provided to stress-test the ITI workflow on two levels: 1) tests that basic parameters are within expected tolerance on the ITI-generated output data; and 2) domain-specific tests that probe the veracity of any end-to-end scientific analysis pipeline that employs the ITI tools.

Downstream analysis routines that make use of ITI may need to be modified to process ITI-generated data differently to directly measured data.

General Validation and Fidelity Testing.

Simple synthetic images (e.g., fields of 2D Gaussians) can be used to check for unanticipated effects in the image generation step. These images can be constructed to help answer specific questions, such as "*Does the ITI model introduce any systemic positional shifts?*" or "*Do the noise properties remain consistent in the presence of bright emission or absorption?*" We have integrated the simple Gaussian field generator with the ITI pipeline to enable end-to-end fidelity tests. This is work in progress and we will present an initial list of 'fidelity' questions to answer. We would like the advisory committee to critique and build on these questions.

Plans for future improvements include adding more complex features (inclined rectangles, non-normal noise and noise gradients) inspired by on-ground EO test structures (e.g, in Bau Tao, China), generating images of turbulence (inspired by astrophysical polarization/magnetism analysis) and integrating statistical tests, and injecting artificial features injected into real data. We also plan to extend the tests to the spectral dimension.

3.f Documentation and Tutorials

For both modules, almost all code has been commented with relevant docstrings.

Heliophysics: We created a wiki page for [heliio_tools](#) to provide the necessary information about the instruments of the space mission used for the heliophysics case studies. Beside that, we are building a [Readthedocs](#) website. This contains extensive documentation and examples of the tool, including installation, information about the download module, the data ingestion module (data loaders), training module, and translation and visualization module.

Earth Observation: There is documentation for the *rs_tools* package available on the [rs_tools github repo](#) and an expanded dedicated documentation webpage provided on the https://spaceml-org.github.io/rs_tools/ website.

4. References and Citations

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Instrument-To-Instrument translation: Instrumental advances drive restoration of solar observation series via deep learning.

[2] Schirninger, C., Veronig A.M., Jarolim R., Johnson, J. E., Jungbluth,A., Galvez, R., Freischem, L., Spalding, A., *Instrument-to-Instrument translation: An AI tool to intercalibrate, enhance and super-resolve solar observations*, EGU General Assembly 2024, EGU24-15813, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-15813>